

FACTORS INFLUENCING PURCHASE PREFERENCE OF WOMEN CONSUMERS TOWARDS TWO WHEELERS

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ABSTRACT

Customer can be defined as an individual who purchases any goods or services from a shop or any business. Customers make decisions regarding any purchase, on the basis of certain internal and external factors. People now, are more brands conscious and they always want to have best from the market. New inventions, technological advancements, improvements in the existing product, and influential advertisements of different competitor brands have opened more options for people to select brands, hence to satisfy the needs. Two wheeler automobile market of India is one of most competitive market in the world and also has emerged into one of the largest automobile market in the world. The two-wheeler market in India is segmented on the basis of scooters, motorcycles, and mopeds. Indian two wheeler market dominates two-third of the market share. In the Scooters segment Honda Activa, TVS Jupiter, Suzuki Access, Honda Dio, and Hero Maestro were the major products. Purpose of this study is how the women purchaser decide while buying the two wheeler, for this study 100 women respondents who purchased two wheeler were randomly selected and with the help of the structured questionnaire data were collected, data were analyzed using SPSS package 20.0 and the findings show that most of them considered value for money as important factor and prefer cash purchase, if company offer credit facilities, the respondents prefer easy EMI.

KEYWORDS: Women consumer, scooter, consumer behaviour, influencing factors, purchase

I - INTRODUCTION

Many factors influencing the purchasing decisions of the consumers, purchase intention of consumers depends on several factors. The customers forever have a preference to go for the product or model which has highest number of features in it. The main factors which

influence the purchase of two wheelers are easy accessibility, service availability in nearby area, functional aspects, and conformance. The useful criteria includes effective suspension system, easily managing in overcrowded traffic or overcrowded roads, satisfying the basic needs of a motorcycle, easy to adjust gear, and long engine life. In the midst of the two wheeler segment, scooters have rising popularity in these days. Scooters are popular for personal transport as it is easier to operate and convenient to park. With upward development, now-a-days we could see about women owing private vehicle as they feel it is more suitable and convenient form of travel. The tendency of using scooters at the present time is a solution to hold up consumer daily movement and the ever-increasing number of sales of scooters shows a excellent indication for two wheeler industry. With the introduction of the government-backed program, Amma Bikes Scheme, which entitles every working woman in Tamil Nadu for a subsidy of 50 percent up to INR 25,000 on the purchase of a scooter, the trade of two-wheelers in the state has gone up. Conversely, the transformation of usual bikes (up to 150 cc) into electric ones had an unfavorable blow on top company in the two-wheeler market. Two-wheelers, with a capacity of up to 150 cc, account for approximately 88 percent of the overall two-wheelers production in India. The target to electrify all these two-wheelers produced by 2025 is a major challenge for giant companies as more than 90 percent of their businesses are constituted of such bikes.

Top 10 Scooters in India				
	Models	February 2020	Models	February 2019
1	Honda Activa	2,22,961	Honda Activa	2,05,239
2	Suzuki Access	50,103	TVS Jupiter	48,688
3	TVS Jupiter	31,440	Suzuki Access	48,265
4	Honda Dio	26,494	Honda Dio	45,017
5	Yamaha Fascino	25,709	Hero Destini 125	24,018
6	TVS NTorq	22,804	TVS NTorq	16,370
7	Yamaha Ray	11,348	Hero Pleasure	15, 264
8	Hero Pleasure	8,435	Yamaha Fascino	14,939
9	Suzuki Burgman Street	7,626	Yamaha Ray	11,700
10	Hero Destini 125	7,304	Hero Maestro	10,223

Source: <https://www.autocarpro.in>

II - REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In a study on factors influencing the students buying behavior of two wheelers, Valarmathi . A (2015) found that the personal factors and product characteristics are important for students' consumers in the process of purchase decision making. The study also found that two-wheeler purchases are driven by different factors such as Better look & style, Pickup and speed, Good mileage, Easy maintenance, new models, after sales and service, Price etc. Sakthivel and Shanthi (2014) have made a study on Perception of women consumers towards the purchase decision of two wheelers in India. The major objective of the study is to analyze the influence of the demographic variables on the factors of purchase decision of women while purchasing two wheelers. The result found that the awareness of women customers towards the two wheeler purchase result differs extensively. Lakshmikanthan, Vijay and Jayachitra (2011) studied on the customer perception towards two wheelers and the study found that Hero Honda is a leading player, with almost 48 percent of two wheeler motorcycle market share. Fahmeeda Yasmeen (2015) made a study on Two-Wheeler Bikes towards Consumer Behaviour and Brand Positioning. Their researches focused on recognize the factors which influence customers in the choice and buy of a specific brand of two-wheeler. The study found that consumers were mostly influenced by parents and friends in the process of buying decision process

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the factors influencing on women consumer purchase decision towards scooters.
- To examine how financial facilities influencing the women consumer purchase decision towards two-wheeler.
- To study the customer satisfaction in association with Brands

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study is to know the factors influencing towards scooter purchase among women buyer and can identify the brand of scooter which influence more among various brands. The study was conducted during January 2020 and February 2020 and the data were

collected from the women scooter users from different category of women such as Government employee, business women, private employees, students, retired person, agricultural related workers and self help group members in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu and the number of sample limited to 100 due to time and money constraints.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was limited to women scooter buyer. The sample size of the study is limited 100. The women who possessed scooters were selected for the study and the study results cannot be generalized as the number of sample is small. The study results may not be applicable in other part of the country. The study was carried out during January 2020 and February 2020.

III - RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Collection of Primary Data

For the current study, the required Primary data have been collected using a survey technique with the help of a well thought-out questionnaire. The data were collected from the respondents regarding their opinion about their purchase and the factors they considered more during the purchase of scooters. The respondents of this study were women scooter buyer. The investigator has totally collected 100 responses for the study. Hence, the sample of 100 is considered for this study.

Collection of Secondary Data

The researcher collected secondary data on scooter sales, market situation, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the purchase action. This information has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

Statistical Tools Used

First hand information is collected from 100 respondents. Responses were coded and data entered and then analysed using a computer programme called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis were used to describe the

sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories, percentage analysis, one-way ANOVA and ranking method were used for this study.

IV - ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table – 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Age	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Age	18-25 Years	17	17.0	17.0
	25-30 Years	20	20.0	37.0
	30-35 Years	28	28.0	65.0
	35-40 Years	11	11.0	76.0
	40-45 Years	15	15.0	91.0
	45 and Above	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Educational Qualification	Below 8th	10	10.0	10.0
	10th Std	15	15.0	25.0
	HSC	7	7.0	32.0
	UG	23	23.0	55.0
	PG	27	27.0	82.0
	M.Phil	9	9.0	91.0
	Others	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Income Level	Less than 5000	27	27.0	27.0
	Rs 5000-10000	22	22.0	49.0
	Rs. 10000-15000	24	24.0	73.0
	Rs 15000-20000	12	12.0	85.0
	Rs. 20000 - 25000	3	3.0	88.0
	Rs. 25000 - 30000	3	3.0	91.0
	Rs. 30000 and above	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Nature of Job	Govt. Employee	12	12.0	12.0
	Business women	6	6.0	18.0
	Private Employees	29	29.0	47.0
	Student	15	15.0	62.0
	Retired Person	2	2.0	64.0
	Farmer	30	30.0	94.0
	Self Help Group	6	6.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	23.0
Brand of Scooter	Honda	23	23.0	23.0
	TVS	37	37.0	60.0

	Yamaha	18	18.0	78.0
	Bajaj	2	2.0	80.0
	Hero	16	16.0	96.0
	Suzuki	4	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	
Duration of Ownership of Two wheeler	1 Year	10	10.0	10.0
	2 Years	28	28.0	38.0
	3 Years	38	38.0	76.0
	4 Years	10	10.0	86.0
	5 Years	10	10.0	96.0
	Above 5 Years	4	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 1 shows the profile of the respondents, among the respondents 20 percent of the respondents belongs to the age group of 25-30 and 28 percent of the respondents belongs to the age group of 30-35 years. Regarding the educational qualification of respondents 27 percent of them are post graduates and 23 percent of them are under graduates and 15 percent of the respondents are having the qualification of 10th standard. In case of income level, 27 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 5000 per month and below, 22 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 5000-10,000 per month, 24 percent of the respondents having the income level of Rs. 1000-15000 per month. Regarding the occupation 30 percent of the respondents are doing farming related works, 29 percent of the respondents are private employees, 15 percent of them are students and 6 percent of the respondents are belongs to self help group. Among the respondents 37 percent of them having TVS vehicle, 23 percent of the respondents having Honda brand of scooters and 18 percent of them having Yamaha. Regarding the years of ownership of the vehicle, 38 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for last 3 years, 28 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for 2 years.

Table -2 Respondents opinion on Mode of purchase

Mode of purchase	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cash	53	53.0	53.0
Bank Loan	23	23.0	76.0
Private Finance	24	24.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 2 show the respondents opinion on mode of purchase when the two wheeler company offers the credit facility. Among the women two wheeler buyer 53 percent of them buy their scooter through cash payment, 23 percent of the respondents will to buy the two wheeler through bank loan and 24 percent of the respondents willing to buy their two wheeler by the way of private finance.

Table – 3 Respondents opinion on Loan offers

Factors	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Low Initial Payment	19	19.0	19.0
Low Rate of Interest	11	11.0	30.0
Low EMI	39	39.0	69.0
Zero Interest	31	31.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 3 show the respondents opinion on factors influencing during the purchase of the two wheeler through Loan offers, here the researcher considered four factors which can be most influential factor such as Low Initial Payment, Low Rate of Interest, Low EMI and Zero interest. In this study it is found that among the respondents 39 percent of the respondents are prefer to buy a two wheeler through Low Equal Monthly Installments (EMI), 31 percent of the respondents prefer to buy a two wheeler through Zero Interest, 19 percent of the respondents prefer to buy a two wheeler through Low Initial Payment and 11 percent of the respondents prefer to buy a two wheeler through Low Rate of Interest.

Table – 4 Respondents opinion on colour of two wheeler they most likely to buy

Factors (Colour)	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Green	13	13.0	13.0
Red	13	13.0	26.0
Black	28	28.0	54.0
Blue	16	16.0	70.0
Other	30	30.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: primary Data

Table – 4 shows the colour of the scooter which the respondents preferred more, product colour is one of the important factor which influence among the women consumer. Among the respondents 30 percent of them prefer to buy colours (pink, silver, orange, brown, white and grey) which we considered as other colours, the respondents preferred black colour (28%) Blue (16%), Green and Red colour (13%).

Table -5 Respondents opinion on Satisfaction in performance

Two Wheeler Attributes	Rank					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Mileage	18	20	19	21	10	12
Price	26	19	13	12	10	20
Pickup	18	15	18	14	16	19
Maintenance	9	13	16	22	25	15
Look and Shape	20	16	12	21	20	11
Brand Image	12	17	23	13	18	17

Source: primary Data

Table – 5 shows respondents opinion towards the performance of the scooter. Respondents were asked to express their opinion and rank the various attributes, and they ranked them. According to the data 26% of the respondents give importance to price factor and they ranked first, 20% of the respondents give importance to mileage and ranked second. And brand image had the respondent's level of 23% followed by maintenance with 22% level and ranked third and fourth rank respectively. The women respondents not given importance to the factors pickup, look and shape.

Table – 6 Respondents opinion on rating the two wheelers

Most Important Factors	Rank			
	1	2	3	4
Value for Money	32	19	10	38
Technology	18	25	32	24
Aesthetic Look	24	28	34	14
Comfort Driving	24	27	23	26

Source: primary Data

Table – 6 shows respondents opinion on rating scale towards the scooter. Among the various factors, the respondents ranked value for money is the primary factors to considered while buying the scooter, and they gives importance to aesthetic look. The respondents gives less importance to technology and comfort driving.

Table -7 Influence of Brands on satisfaction

Brand	N	Mean	SD	F-Value	p-value
Honda	23	4.70	.470	34.840	.000
TVS	37	2.35	.676		
Yamaha	18	4.33	.485		
Bajaj	2	4.00	1.414		
Hero	16	3.31	1.078		
Suzuki	4	3.25	1.500		
Total	100	3.47	1.218		

Source: primary Data

Table – 7 shows the satisfaction level of respondents among various brands of scooters. To know the satisfaction level of respondents among various brands one way ANOVA was carried out. The result shows that there is a significant difference on respondent's satisfaction level (.000). Honda scooter users have more satisfaction than other brands because the mean value shows 4.70 than other brands of scooters. The study results shows that Honda scooter user have more satisfaction than other brand users.

V - FINDINGS

From the study it is found that among the respondents the maximum number of respondents belong to the age group of 30-35 years. In educational qualification of respondents 27 percent of them are post graduates and 23 percent of them are under graduates. Regarding the occupation 30 percent of the respondents are doing farming related works, 29 percent of the respondents are private employees, 15 percent of them are students and 6 percent of the respondents are belongs to self help group. Among the respondents 37 percent of them having TVS scooters, 23 percent of the respondents having Honda brand of scooters 18 percent of them having Yamaha brands. Regarding the years of ownership of the vehicle, 38 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for last 3 years, 28 percent of the respondents owning the vehicle for 2 years.

The study result shows that even though the two wheeler companies offer credit facilities 53 percent of them buy their scooter through cash payment, 23 percent of the respondents preferred to buy through bank loans and 24 percent of them prefer to private finance. It is concluded that the respondents prefer to buy through cash than bank loan and private finance.

From the study it is concluded that among the respondents most of them prefer Low EMI (39%) offers during the two wheeler purchase, followed by Zero interest by (31%) and Low Initial Payment preferred by (19%) respondents and finally considered as least factor is (11%) Low Rate of Interest. The study found that the women respondent gives importance to selection of their two wheeler colours. The study results shows that the women respondents give more importance to price and considered as one of the influencing factor and give less importance to mileage and brand image, the respondents not at all given importance to pickup, look and shape

The result shows that among the various factors, the respondents ranked value for money is the primary factors to considered while buying the scooter, and they gives importance to aesthetic look. The respondents give less importance to technology and comfort driving. Honda scooter users have more satisfaction than other brands among the women two wheeler buyer.

VI - CONCLUSION

Marketing plays an important role in today's world and the global market competition also growing. Hence, there is a need to fulfill the needs and wants of the customer's and hence can increase the satisfaction which can lead the customer retention. It is responsibility of the producer to understanding the factors which affect customer satisfaction. Two wheeler marketplace of India is one of most aggressive market in the world and also has emerged into one of the leading automobile market. Today the automobile industry has witnessed backward growth due to various reasons, keeping in mind the present scenario the two wheeler maker should satisfy the customer needs.

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